

WEST AFRICAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATION AND PLANNING (WAJEAP)

VOL 1, NO. 1
ISSN: 3026-9202

**WEST AFRICAN JOURNAL OF
EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATION
AND PLANNING (WAJEAP)**

ISSN: 3026-9202

Vol. 1 , December, 2023

A Publication of

The University of Sierra Leone, Sierra Leone

Editorial Board

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. M.O.B. Mohammed

*Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education,
Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos Nigeria*

Email: mubashiru.mohammed@lasu.edu.ng

08033344750

Consulting Editors

1. Prof Jonas A S Redwood-Sawyerr,
*Executive Director, eLearning Centre,
University of Sierra Leone*
2. Prof Ronnie Frazer-Williams
*Dean, School of Postgraduate Studies,
University of Sierra Leone*
3. Onoriode Collins Potokri PhD
*Education Leadership and Management
Faculty of Education, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
cpotokri@uj.ac.za*
4. Prof Ayeni Abiodun Olumide
*University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria
Faculty of Education,
Department of Educational Management
Email: biodunmide@gmail.com*
5. Prof George Oduro
*University of Cape coast,
Institute for Educational Planning and Administration, Ghana
Email: goduro@ucc.edu.gh*

CONTENTS

The Use of Lichens as Bio-Indicators and a Cost-Effective way for Heavy Metals Pollution Monitoring in Ambient Air in The Western Area and Southern Province of Sierra Leone Abdul Sannoh & Ronnie. A.D. Frazer-Williams -----	1-13
Academic Mentorship and Lecturers' Productivity in Public Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria SHITTU, Taofeek Olawale; OLA, Bolanle Adeyemi & ADEPOJU, Funke Femi -----	14-20
Paradoxes of the use of Technologies in Secondary Education System in Africa Femi Sunday Akinwumi & Adeola Iyabosola Ayo-Ayinde -----	21-30
Social Insecurity and Proneness to Get- Rich-Quick-Syndrome among Adolescents in Lagos State, Nigeria: Counselling for National Development A. O. Badejo & Stella Ngozi Chinwuba-Anameje -----	31-40
Design and Production of an Improved Cook Stove with Swinging Combustion Chamber to Enable Refueling for Continuous Operation Sheriff Kamara -----	41-59
Teachers' Welfare as a Veritable Tool for Effectiveness among Public Secondary Schools In Lagos State, Nigeria Ladipo, Sunday Akinremi -----	60-63
Free Education Program in Sub Saharan Africa: A Comparative Analysis of Sierra Leone and Nigeria James VIBBI & Abidat Oluwashola MOHAMMED -----	64-76
Managing Education for Innovation and Security in the Development of Sub-Shara Africa: Policy Formulation and Implementation Option John Oluyemi EGBEBI & Opeyemi Aderonke OYEKAN -----	77-85
Cross-Cultural Influences on Girl-Child Education in Ojo Riverine Area of Lagos State, Nigeria Enitan Omolara Falade & Prof. Olawunmi Ayodeji Badejo -----	86-92
Establishing a School Climate That Prioritizes Child Safety to Promote Sustainable National Development Henry Adewale Odunayo; Nurudeen Olalekan Orunbon & M. O. B. Mohammed -----	93-102
Gender Equality: A Must for Sustainable Development in Africa Aisha Fofana Ibrahim & Claudine Anita Hingston -----	103-110
Teachers' Reward System and Academic Performance of Public Senior Secondary School Students in Lagos State, Nigeria ANIFOWOSHE, Olawale Jamiu & MOHAMMED, M. O. B. -----	111-116

Records Management Practices and Productivity of Academic Heads of Department in Public Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria Afolabi, Abolanle Omotunde; Shittu, Taofeek Olawale & Mohammed, M. O. B. -----	117-124
Estimating Rainfall Intensity Duration-Frequency (IDF) Curves for River Rokel Catchment in Tonkolili District Using Satellite Rainfall Data Amadu Barrie; Osman Koroma & Melvin B Scott -----	125-135
Religious Education, Security Challenges, and National Development in Nigeria Exradallenum Olusegun Akinsanya, Opaaje, Samuel Sunday & Aina, Omololu Olukayode -----	136-147
Integrating Sustainable Water Resources Management Practices into Public University Administration in Lagos State, Nigeria: A Multi-Variable Analysis Adepoju, Funke Femi -----	148-155
Examining the Nexus between Inadequate Educational Facilities as Proxy for Migration and Personal Remittance in Nigeria: Impact on Socio-Economic Development Rufai, Musiliu Dada; Anagun, Adeyemi Michael & Olayide, Bilkis Omolara	156-165

TEACHERS' REWARD SYSTEM AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

ANIFOWOSHE, Olawale Jamiu

Phone Number: +2348023000154

Email: anifowosheoj@yahoo.com

MOHAMMED, M. O. B.

Phone Number: +2348033344750

Email: myuniversity@yahoo.com

Department of Educational Management, Lagos State University, Lagos, Nigeria

Abstract

This paper examined teachers' reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational design. The population of the study comprised all teachers in 322 public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised, and two null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. A sample of 300 respondents was drawn through simple random sampling techniques. Two research instruments titled 'Teachers' Reward System Questionnaire' (TRSQ) and 'Records Observation Format' (ROF) were used for data collection. The content validity of the instruments was ensured by test experts and the reliability consistency of the instruments was 0.65 using Cronbach's alpha. Kendall's tau-b correlation was used to analyse data collected via Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22.0. The findings of hypotheses 1 and 2 showed that a significant relationship existed between teachers' tangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .521$; $N=300$; $p<0.05$); and a significant relationship existed between teachers' intangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .620$; $N=300$; $p<0.05$). Based on the findings, the study concluded that teachers' morale and students' academic performance in public secondary schools will increase if the reward system and remunerated package are catered for by the government. Therefore, it is recommended amongst others that government should enhance the remuneration package of teachers and reward their hard work with promotion at the right time.

Keywords: Reward System, Remuneration Package, Students' Performance and Public School

Introduction

All over the world, any educational institution that employs teachers sets up systems to reward them because teaching is regarded as a noble profession. Teachers are the human component of a school system, and they are the most important factor that determines the quality of teaching and student potential in terms of "value-added. Teachers could be rewarded financially and non- financially to impart knowledge to the students. Teachers' reward systems inspire teaching within the lifeblood of secondary education and one of the major reasons for rewarding teachers is to improve their job satisfaction which translates to better status and quality of teaching (Rakiro, 2016). As such, teachers' reward systems are a

good example of managerial approaches that easily inspire teaching in secondary school education and just like in other organizations, reward systems have been key influencers of job satisfaction. Teachers' rewards come in two flavours: Tangible and intangible. The term "tangible rewards" refers to benefits that are concrete, obvious, and simple to measure, including pay and promotions. Tangible rewards are those which an employee receives from his or her organization after good performance or after accomplishing a specific task. These rewards include gifts, promotions, salary increases, remuneration and bonuses. Teachers' intangible rewards are Prizes, plaques, and trophies presented at yearly celebrations for exemplary achievement. Tangible rewards are necessary because employees are rewarded for their personal satisfaction, to make them feel better in the organization. These types of rewards include empowerment, trust, recognition, information and feedback. According to Khan, Forooq and Ullah (2010), remuneration is a vital factor which affects teachers' morale.

However, the reward system is an important tool that management uses to influence employee motivation. In other words, management uses a reward system to attract people to join the organisation, keep them coming to work and motivate them to perform to high levels (Agwu, 2013). The reward could be financial and non-financial. A reward system includes financial incentives like as basic salary, bonuses, commissions, and overtime payments, which together make up total compensation. Reward systems may also include non-cash components, such as recognition, appreciation, a work-life balance, a positive work environment, and possibilities for professional advancement. A key component of human resource motivation is the rewards system. According to Wilton (2011), focusing on the following functions of Human Resource Management can make the organization realize its objectives: performance, resourcing, reward, training and development and employee relations. Rewards are used to improve performance. A basic salary is one of the rights of a normal working person but also a motivating reward. Akuoko (2012) argued that salaries and allowances improved the performance of teachers. Given their duty to impart knowledge and skills to students, teacher motivation has grown to be a crucial issue. It is argued that satisfied teachers are generally more productive and can influence students' achievement (Mark, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, the academic performance of secondary school students in Lagos State has become worrisome and bedevilled with challenges of teachers' reward system which culminated in teachers' turnover and brain-drain syndrome. Incidentally, a number of factors have been observed as clogs on the wheels of progress like poor remuneration and intangible reward system for teachers, and more importantly, failure of the state government to implement the agreed 27.5% increment could be contributory factors to teachers' low morale, absenteeism, late-coming, failure to assess students' works, lack of sense of belonging and redundancy at work. All these are indicators of a poor level of job performance. This adversely put Lagos State to continue witnessing a tremendous decline in the academic performance of public secondary school students. Looking at this catastrophic situation is proof that the last ten years have recorded 50 per cent failure in WAEC, NECO and JAMB examinations. Students now have a popular term to describe examination malpractices with a special WAEC examination 'Miracle Centre' where examination malpractices are "officially" allowed at the payment of a certain amount of funds.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to:

1. examine the relationship between teachers' tangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria.
2. determine the relationship between teachers' intangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were raised:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' tangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' intangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical anchorage of the study hinged on the Expectancy theory by Vroom (1964) which emphasizes the idea that individuals are motivated by expected outcomes that they value. Expectancy is the process that an individual undergoes to make choices. The theory emphasizes the need for government to relate rewards directly to performance and to ensure that the rewards provided are those rewards deserved and wanted by the recipient. The theory explains the behavioural process through which individuals choose one behavioural option over another. It also explains how they make decisions to achieve the end they value. This expectancy-value model states that a behaviour is motivated by the subjective probability of successfully reaching the behavioural goal. The theory states that three perceptions can affect a person's motivation: valence, instrumentality and expectancy. Valence refers to the degree to which an individual value the consequences of a specific goal. Instrumentality refers to the connection between achieving the goal and experiencing the consequences. Expectancy refers to the belief that the person has about whether he or she can reach the goal (Vroom, 1964). Expectancy theory has implications for teacher pay changes. The changes in pay must be valued by teachers. Any monetary reward or incentive must be consequential enough so that teachers regard it as being worthwhile. Teachers must perceive that they can and will attain positive rewards before they will be motivated. An increase in pay or bonuses must be funded in a stable way such a weak economy does not affect the payment process.

Methodology

The research design was descriptive survey and correlational. The target population comprised of all teachers in the public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria. The sample size comprised of 300 teachers randomly selected using simple random sampling techniques for the study. A structured instrument titled: 'Teachers' Reward System Questionnaire' (TRSQ) and 'Records Observation Format' (ROF) were designed by the researcher. The questionnaires were administered to all selected teachers in public senior secondary schools of the six Education Districts in Lagos State, Nigeria. Fifty teachers were randomly selected from each of the six Education Districts. The structured questionnaire was divided into two sections: Section A and B. Section A contains the personal information of the respondents and section B contains the questionnaire items structured around the research questions. Each statement is measured on a four-point modifier Likert-type-rating scale, namely: "Strongly Agree (SA) on 4 points", "Agree (A) on 3 points", "Strongly

Disagree (SD) on 2 points” and “Disagree (D) on 1point”. The data collected were properly analyzed using Kendall's tau-b correlation coefficient. The content validity of the instruments was scrutinized by test experts and the reliability index of the instrument was persistently determined through Cronbach’s alpha at 0.65 meaning that the instrument is reliable.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between teachers’ tangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Correlations			Teachers’ Tangible Reward System	Students’ Academic Performance
Kendall's tau_b	Teachers’_ Tangible Reward System	Correlation	1.000	.521
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
	Students'_Academic Performance	N	300	300
		Correlation	.521	1.000
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	300	300

Source: Field Survey (2023) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall's tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between teachers’ tangible reward system and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between teachers’ tangible reward system and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .521$; $N=300$; $p<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that “there is no significant relationship between teachers’ tangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected and alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicated the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between teachers’ tangible reward system and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria. This finding corroborated with Ansarud and Adebajo (2014) study on the reward system and employee’s performance in Lagos State revealed that there is a significant relationship between employee’s performance and salary package. Based on this premise, effective remuneration by the organization enhances performance and rewards can have a major impact not only on morale and productivity but also its ability to attract and retain staff. The finding also negates Yego (2017) noted that both promotion and recognition had a negative influence on employee output.

Table 2: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between teachers' intangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Correlations			Teachers' Intangible Reward System	Students' Academic Performance
Kendall's tau_b	Teachers'_ Intangible Reward System	Correlation	1.000	.620
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
	N		300	300
	Students'_ Academic Performance	Correlation	.620	1.000
		Coefficient		
Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.	
N		300	300	

Source: Field Survey (2023) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall's tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between teachers' intangible reward system and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between teachers' intangible reward system and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .620$; $N=300$; $p<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that "there is no significant relationship between teachers' intangible reward system and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected and alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicated the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between teachers' intangible reward system and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria. This finding supported Ezeala, Maxwell and Amadi (2017) who are of the view that money has the purchasing power to recruit teachers, and pay their salaries and allowances. Financial resources should be made available so as to reward teachers promptly. The finding also corroborated with supported a study by Salman, Mohammed, Ogunlade, and Ayinla (2012) has found that the majority of teachers and students have agreed that payment of poor remuneration, in terms of salary and allowances for teachers, affects their performance which as a result contributed greatly to students' mass failure in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study concluded that salary or earnings are the primary compensation for teachers to perform their work. Along with salaries and wages, management and the government also provide pension benefits, paid lunches, childcare, health insurance, official cars, advantageous loans, bonuses, and numerous other benefits. Reward systems motivate teachers to perform their teaching better. It can be categorised as a tangible and intangible reward system. According to the study's findings, teacher reward programs should also be commensurate with the work that each teacher puts forth and comparable to those of other businesses of a similar calibre that operate in an economy.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should be given promotions, wage raises, and additional compensation.
2. Government should increase teachers' pay and recognize their efforts with promotions at the appropriate times.
3. Promotions should be given to teachers in the senior secondary public institutions in Lagos State to boost morale.
4. Government should ensure that teachers are paid fairly for the work they do.
5. School authorities should sensitize teachers about the value of performance-based rewarding.

References

- Agwu, M. O. (2013). Impact of fair reward system in employees job performance in Nigerian Agip Oil Company. *British Journal of Education, Society & Behavioural Science* 3(1), 47-64.
- Akuoko, K. & Kanwettu (2012). Performance Appraisal as Employee Motivation Mechanism in Selected Financial Institutions in Kumasi, Ashanti Region of Ghana. *Zenith International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2,15-21.
- Ansarud, I. & Adebajo, O. E. (2014). Reward system and employee's performance in Lagos State: A study of selected public secondary schools. *South Africa journal of industrial psychology* 31(4), 25-39.
- Ezeala, I. L., Maxwell, D. & Amadi, M. C. (2017). Financial cost commitment of principals in economic recession and management at secondary schools in Rivers State. *African Journal of educational research and development* 9(3), 275-287.
- Khan, K. U., Farooq, S. U., & Ullah, M. I. (2010). The relationship between rewards and employee motivation in commercial banks of Pakistan. *Research journal of international studies*, 5(14),37-52.
- Mark, A. (2015). Factor influencing teacher's motivation and job performance in Kibaha district, Tanzania. *ACTORS INFLUENCING*. Available at http://repository.out.ac.tz/1413/1/Mark_Agnes_-_DESSERTATION-24-
- Rakiro, L.A. (2016). Effects of institutional teacher reward systems on students' performance in Kenya certificate of secondary education in Rongo District, Kenya. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 7(3), 809-837.
- Salman, M.F., Mohammed, A. S., Ogunlade A. A., & Ayinla, J.O. (2012). Causes of Mass Failure in Senior School Certificate Mathematics Examinations as Viewed by Secondary School Teachers and Students in Ondo, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(8), 79-89.
- Yego, E. M. (2017). *Influence of Teacher Reward System on Employees Output: A Case of Public Primary Schools, Turbo Division, Uasin Gishu County, Kenya*. (Masters Dissertation, University of Nairobi).